

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Yield of rice under chronic air pollution stress, as influenced by soil nitrogen

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We evaluated the response of varieties Co 43, GR3, and TKM9 to chronic air pollution by a fertilizer plant (GSFC in Baroda, India) during 1985 wet season. Seeds were exposed 350 m in the windward direction from the pollution source. Air pollutant daily averages at the test site were 16.5 µg SO₂/m³, 25 µg NO_x/m³, 16.4 mg NH₃/m³, 0.403 µM F/cm², and 233.7 µg suspended particulate matter/m³.

Table 1. Effect of air pollution on the yield attributes of rice cultivars.^a Baroda, India.

Cultivar	Regime	Panicle length (cm)		Panicles/plant		Spikelets/panicle		Filled grains/plant		Unfilled grains/plant	
		C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P
Co 43	LN	16.5	10.5	2.6	3.8	7.3	4.8	131.0	1.4	61.0	180.8
	HN	15.2	14.4	3.0	4.0	6.3	6.1	127.0	17.6	68.6	191.8
GR3	LN	18.8	14.0	2.8	11.2	8.6	6.9	116.2	156.2	45.0	264
	HN	15.8	14.4	4.2	11.6	7.9	6.9	50.0	246.2	95.8	271
TKM9	LN	16.6	13.9	3.4	6.0	5.3	5.2	102.8	125.2	43.0	156.8
	HN	14.7	11.8	3.8	5.0	5.0	4.3	52.8	47.2	50.0	107.8
Mean		16.3	13.2	3.3	6.9	6.7	5.7	96.6	88.0	60.6	195.4
CD (0.05)		2.60		3.90		2.73		3.70		2.50	

^aC = control, P = polluted, LN = low nitrogen, HN = high nitrogen.

At 30 d after seeding, seedlings potted in 8 kg soil were fertilized with N as urea (low level, 0.069 g N/pot 2 times; high, 1.69 g N/pot 3 times). Controls

were maintained 10 km away from the test site, using the same soil and water: GR3 performed better under high N and TKM9 under low N (Table 1,2). □

Table 2. Effect of air pollution on yield of rice cultivars. Baroda, India.

Cultivar	Regime	Dry wt (g) of filled grains/plant		Dry wt (g) of unfilled grains/plant		Straw wt (g/plant)		100-grain wt (g)		Yield (g)		Harvest index	
		C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P
Co 43	LN	1.81	0.02	0.15	0.35	3.19	7.97	3.19	1.20	5.19	8.34	0.361	0.002
	HN	1.63	0.19	0.12	0.42	3.36	5.56	3.36	1.10	6.74	6.17	0.309	0.031
GR3	LN	1.90	2.32	0.20	1.21	3.02	5.38	3.02	5.38	5.12	8.81	0.365	0.256
	HN	0.74	3.75	0.43	1.31	2.71	5.55	2.71	5.55	3.89	10.05	0.184	0.377
TKM9	LN	1.66	2.10	0.15	0.65	2.84	3.67	2.84	3.66	4.65	6.42	0.363	0.293
	HN	0.84	0.75	0.21	0.36	2.63	3.02	2.63	3.02	3.68	4.13	0.231	0.180
Mean		1.43	1.52	0.21	0.72	2.96	5.19	2.87	3.32	4.88	7.32	0.302	0.190
CD (0.05)		0.59		0.29		1.29		0.07		1.86		0.005	

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Identification and classification of fertility restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile line V20A

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Since rice is a strictly self-pollinated crop, heterosis breeding must have an effective male sterility and restorer system to produce a bulk quantity of hybrid seeds. Among the commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile lines, V20A is one of the most stable.

V20A was crossed with 40 indica varieties to identify their fertility-

restoring ability and the maintenance capacity of V20A. The F₁s were raised in 4 replications, each consisting of 40 plots with an interplot spacing of 50 cm. Each plot had 1 row of 5 single-plant hills, with a spacing of 25 cm between hills. At maturity, all plants were harvested, and their grain fertility calculated. The varieties were then

classified according to grain fertility percentage. Of the 40 varieties studied, 19 were classified as restorers, 12 as partial restorers, and 9 as maintainers (see table). □

Fertility restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers of cytoplasmic male sterile line V20A. Bihar, India.

Variety or line	Grain fertility (%)
<i>Restorer (> 7.5% fertility)</i>	
RAU4045-2A	89.6
IR19748-28	88.8
BAU120-9	88.5
IR58	88.5
IR19728-3-2-3-3	88.0
IR54	85.7
IR36	85.5
IR60	85.4
Amrose	84.4
BAU146-9-2	82.9
BAU151-51	82.7
IRAT-112	82.1
RAU4045-6	81.9
BAU147-22	81.9
BAU151-54	81.3
IR50	77.9
IR24	77.9
P-33	77.7
OR165-28-4	75.7
<i>Partial restorer (10- 7.5% fertility)</i>	
Pusa 2-21	65.3
RAU4045-3	60.0
IR8	53.3
Kiran	49.3
Changlei	45.8
Culture-1	27.4
RP1848-21-3-5	21.3
Ratna	20.2
BAU151-56	17.2
Badshah Pasand	15.0
Saket-4	10.1
BAU122-2	10.1
<i>Maintainer (<10% fertility)</i>	
Bala	8.3
CR404-48	6.8
CH1039	6.5
IET7918	6.2
Annapurna	6.1
CH988	4.8
ADT30	4.2
CR407-19	3.8
Cauvery	3.2
CD (P=0.05)	6.66
CV = 9.00%	

Isozyme markers to monitor seed purity in indica hybrid rice

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Simple genetic markers are needed to assess the efficiency of systems for

Table 1. Discriminative power of isozyme markers among indica rices: probability (P) that 2 randomly chosen varieties differ for each individual marker and for a certain number of markers. IRRI, 1985.

Object of comparison	P
<i>Individual marker^a</i>	
<i>Amp-1</i> (2)	0.13
Block (<i>Amp-3</i> , <i>Est-2</i>) ^b (3)	0.61
<i>Pgi-2</i> (3)	0.50
<i>Pgi-1</i> (4)	0.13
<i>Sdh-1</i> (6)	0.52
<i>Pox-2</i> ^c (6)	0.50
<i>Acp-1</i> (6)	0.04
<i>Est-9</i> (7)	0.45
<i>Amp-2</i> (8)	0.02
<i>Adh-1</i> (11)	0.02
<i>Pgd-1</i> (11)	0.55
<i>Est-1</i> ^c (?)	0.06
<i>Acp-4</i> (?)	0.39
<i>Mal-1</i> (?)	0.04
<i>Number of markers</i>	
0	0.00
1	0.03
2	0.11
3	0.21
4	0.26
5	0.21
6	0.11
7	0.04
8	0.01
9	0.00
>9	

^aChromosome number in parentheses. ^bBlock of 2 tightly linked loci, showing strong linkage disequilibrium. ^cInvolving one null allele (recessive) in significant frequency.

Table 2. Variation at 10 loci among 6 CMS, 4 B, and 8 R lines of the WA cyto sterility system. IRRI, 1987.

Line	Plants analyzed (no.)	Most frequent allelic constitution at 10 loci ^a										Frequency (%) of other types
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10*	
<i>A lines</i>												
Zhen Shan 97A	156	1	2*	2*	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	2*	32.1
V20A	88	1	1*	2*	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	2*	31.8
IR46830A	801	2*	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	5.0
IR54752A	605	1	1*	1*	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	1	0.5
IR54753A	167	1	1*	1	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	1	0.6
IR54754A	88	1	1	1	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	1	1.1
<i>B lines</i>												
Zhen Shan 97	114	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	0
V20A	102	1	1*	2*	1	1	2	1*	1*	2*	2*	8.8
IR46830	144	1	2	1*	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2.8
IR54752	104	1	1*	1	1	1	2*	2*	1	1*	1	2.9
<i>R lines</i>												
Milyang 46	147	1	1	4*	1	1	2	2*	1	1*	2	0.7
Milyang 54	110	1	2	1	1	1	2	1*	0	2*	1	15.5
IR9761-19-1	104	1	1*	1	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	1	6.7
IR13292-5-3	213	1	2	1	1	1	2	2*	0	1*	2*	8.5
IR14753-120-3	154	1	2*	1*	1	1	2	1*	0	2*	1	9.7
IR19392-211-1	117	1	2*	1	1	1	2	1*	1	2*	1	11.1
IR20933-68-21-1-2	110	1	2	1*	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1.8
IR54R	131	1	2*	1*	1	1	2	1	0*	2	1	5.3

^a1 = *Pgi-1*, 2 = *Pgi-2*, 3 = *Sdh-1*, 4 = *Adh-1*, 5 = *Amp-1*, 6 = *Amp-2*, 7 = *Amp-3*, 8 = *Est-1*, 9 = *Est-2*, 10 = *Est-9*, 1 = locus where several alleles have been found within the line.

hybrid seed production by differentiating the seeds resulting from the expected combination from those produced by selfing and those produced by foreign pollen.

We investigated polymorphism of genes coding for isozymes among the indica rices to determine their potential to address this matter. The survey of 900 traditional varieties identified 14 polymorphic genes expressed in young shoots, among which 9 are highly polymorphic. Thus, isozymes provide a very powerful means of discrimination among indica rices (Table 1).

We used some of these enzymes to characterize six cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS), four maintainer (B), and eight restorer (R) lines for the wild aborted (WA) cyto sterility system (Table 2). Each line presents a dominant allelic combination, with minor combinations observed in variable frequencies. The dominant combination in any CMS line is different from that in any R line. Thus, after preliminary purification, these genes will be useful in determining hybrid seed purity. □